

A Simple Test for Technological Change in the Input-Output Model

Luis Frank¹

¹DNMyP, Ministerio de Economía, Av. Hipólito Yrigoyen 250, C1086AAB
Argentina.

Abstract

The input-output (IO) model is widely used to predict the impact of a sectoral demand shock on other sectors of the economy. The model is essentially a linear transformation of demand into a production vector, with the transformation matrix being a function of the so-called technological matrix. The technological matrix is derived from the Supply and Use Tables (SUTs) of the National Accounts System and is typically updated whenever the National Accounts Office updates the SUTs. However, no statistical test has yet been proposed to compare whether the differences between two alternative technological matrices are significant enough to justify replacing one with the other. This paper proposes a test based on the Wald chi-square statistic and applies it to a set of simulated SUTs. The report concludes by discussing the types of (technological) hypotheses that could be tested with the new test and some of its limitations.

Keywords: Input-Output model, technological change, National Accounts, Supply and Use Tables, Wald statistic, χ^2

1. Introduction

The Input-Output (IO) or Leontief model is widely used to estimate the multiplier effect of a sectoral demand shock on the production across all sectors of an economy. The model's formulation varies depending on the classification criteria for macroeconomic aggregates in each country's National Accounts System (NAS). In Argentina, the most common version, known as the "industry technology" model (DESASD, 1999), classifies both supply and demand by sector or industry rather than by product. In this framework, the sectoral supply vector is expressed as a linear transformation of the final demand vector, also classified by sector. This transformation relies on two matrices from the NAS: the Supply and Use Tables (SUTs). Through algebraic operations, these tables yield the matrix of technical coefficients. Let \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{D}_I denote the supply and use tables, respectively. Then, the IO model is then expressed as:

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{d}_F, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the $k \times 1$ supply vector representing the production of k sectors, $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{D}_I \mathbf{T}_k^{-1}$ is the $k \times k$ matrix of technical coefficients of dimension (also known as the direct requirements matrix), $(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1}$ is the Leontief inverse or multiplier matrix, and \mathbf{d}_F is the final demand vector. The term "multiplier matrix" reflects its ability to show the multiplier effect of a unit increase in a sector's final demand on the entire economy. The matrices \mathbf{T}_n and \mathbf{T}_k are diagonal, with non-zero elements corresponding to the sums of the elements by row and column, respectively, of \mathbf{S} . These matrices satisfy the identities $\mathbf{T}_k^{-1} \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{1}_n = \mathbf{1}_k$ and $\mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{1}_k = \mathbf{1}_n$. Each coefficient a_{ij} in \mathbf{A} represents the proportion of inputs from the i -th sector used in the production of the j -th sector, with all coefficients bounded in $[0, 1]$ and the sum of coefficients in any row or column less than one.

The technical coefficients reflect the prevailing technology at a given time and are assumed fixed unless the technology changes. However, detecting technological change through these coefficients is challenging, as SUTs are typically constructed from sample-based data, scaled from input and product baskets reported by firms. This paper proposes a straightforward method to compare technological matrices and identify potential technological changes.

2. The Technological Change Test

Consider two pairs of SUTs compiled at different times: \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{D}_I for the first pair, and \mathbf{S}^* and \mathbf{D}_I^* for the second, all of dimension $n \times k$. Assume that \mathbf{S}^* is related to \mathbf{S} through the transformation $\mathbf{S}^* = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{\Pi}_S$, where $\mathbf{\Pi}_S$ is a $k \times k$ diagonal matrix whose j -th non-zero element represents the increase in production of the j -th activity due to a new production technique. Similarly, $\mathbf{D}_I^* = \mathbf{D}_I\mathbf{\Pi}_D$, where $\mathbf{\Pi}_D$ is a diagonal matrix similar to $\mathbf{\Pi}_S$ whose non-zero elements reflect reductions in input use due to a presumably more efficient production technique. The term ‘‘presumably’’ acknowledges that input reductions could result from increased labor use without efficiency gains, though this is economically unlikely. In the presence of technological change, one expects $\pi_{jj}^S \geq 1$ and/or $\pi_{jj}^D \leq 1$, while in the absence of technological change, all π_{jj}^S and π_{jj}^D equal one.

To incorporate the $\mathbf{\Pi}$ matrices into the Leontief model, consider the identities

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{T}_k^{-1}\mathbf{S}^*\mathbf{1}_n = \mathbf{1}_k \iff \mathbf{T}_k^{-1}\mathbf{\Pi}'_S\mathbf{T}_k\mathbf{T}_k^{-1}\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{1}_n = \mathbf{1}_k \\ \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{S}^*\mathbf{1}_k = \mathbf{1}_n \iff \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{\Pi}_S\mathbf{1}_k = \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{1}_k \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

From these, $\mathbf{T}_k^* = \mathbf{\Pi}'_S\mathbf{T}_k$ and $(\mathbf{S}\mathbf{\Pi}_S)'\mathbf{T}_n^{*-1} = \mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}$. Substituting \mathbf{S}^* and \mathbf{D}_I^* into the technological matrix $\mathbf{A}^* = \mathbf{S}^*\mathbf{T}_n^{*-1}\mathbf{D}_I^*\mathbf{T}_k^{*-1}$, we obtain

$$\mathbf{A}^* = (\mathbf{S}\mathbf{\Pi}_S)'\mathbf{T}_n^{*-1}(\mathbf{D}_I\mathbf{\Pi}_D)(\mathbf{\Pi}'_S\mathbf{T}_k)^{-1} = (\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{D}_I\mathbf{T}_k^{-1})(\mathbf{T}_k\mathbf{\Pi}_D\mathbf{T}_k^{-1}\mathbf{\Pi}_S^{-1}) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}. \quad (3)$$

This result demonstrates that technological change in the Leontief model acts as a linear transformation of the technical coefficients matrix. The transformation matrix \mathbf{B} resembles the matrix that post-multiplies \mathbf{A} in the RAS biproportional adjustment method (Miller & Blair 2009, chapter 7) when technological change excludes input substitution. However, \mathbf{B} is not directly observable and cannot be calculated as $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{A}^*$, since \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{A}^* are empirical estimators, and their product is unlikely to yield a diagonal matrix or satisfy $a_{ij}^* = \mathbf{a}'_i\mathbf{b}_j \leq 1$. Thus, the relationship between \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{A}^* is better modeled as a multivariate regression $\mathbf{A}^*|\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} + \mathbf{E}$. In vectorized form:

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{A}^*|\mathbf{A}) = (\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}) \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}) + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad \text{where } \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim N(\mathbf{0}_{k^2}, \sigma^2\mathbf{I}_{k^2}). \quad (4)$$

2.1 Estimation of the Technological Change Matrix

To estimate \mathbf{B} , a restricted estimator is required to ensure that all non-diagonal elements of \mathbf{B} are zero. The constraints are expressed as $\mathbf{R}_{q \times k^2} \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{0}_{kq \times 1}$, where $q = k^2 - k$. The constraint system is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_1 & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \dots & & \mathbf{R}_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_q \\ \mathbf{0}_q \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{0}_q \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Each block \mathbf{R}_j is an identity matrix of dimension $k \times k$ without the j -th row, with dimension $(k - 1) \times k$. For example,

$$\mathbf{R}_j = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The restricted least squares estimator, following Greene and Seaks (1991) and Kikawa & Kloppers (2016) (see Appendix A), solves the system:

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A}) & \mathbf{R}' \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{0}_{q \times q} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R) \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}')\text{vec}(\mathbf{A}^*) \\ \mathbf{0}_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Here, \mathbf{R} denotes the restricted estimator, and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is a vector of Lagrange multipliers. The estimator and its variance are:

$$\begin{cases} \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R) = \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}) - \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] \mathbf{R}' \left\{ \mathbf{R} \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] \mathbf{R}' \right\}^{-1} [\mathbf{R} \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}) - \mathbf{0}_q] \\ \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)] = \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] - \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] \mathbf{R}' \left\{ \mathbf{R} \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] \mathbf{R}' \right\}^{-1} \mathbf{R} \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}|\mathbf{A}) = [\mathbf{I}_k \otimes (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}] (\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}') \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}^*) \\ \quad = (\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}^{-1}) \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}^*) \\ \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}|\mathbf{A})] = \sigma^2 [\mathbf{I}_k \otimes (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}] \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The simplification of $\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})$ is possible because \mathbf{A} is square. The computation of $\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})$ and $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)]$ requires the inverse of $\mathbf{R} \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] \mathbf{R}'$ to exist. Since $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})]$ is symmetric, it can be decomposed via Cholesky decomposition as $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}})] = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}'$. Replacing the ordinary inverse with a generalized inverse, the variance of the restricted estimator becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)]^* &= \sigma^2 \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}' - \sigma^2 \mathbf{L}(\mathbf{R}\mathbf{L})' [(\mathbf{R}\mathbf{L})(\mathbf{R}\mathbf{L})']^{-1} (\mathbf{R}\mathbf{L})\mathbf{L}' \\ &= \sigma^2 \mathbf{L} [\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{P}'\mathbf{P})^{-1} \mathbf{P}'] \mathbf{L}' \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the projector $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{P}'\mathbf{P})^{-1} \mathbf{P}'$ is invariant to the chosen inverse (see Lütkepohl 1996, p. 32, §3.6.1 item 4). This result is extremely important, as it ensures the existence of the covariance matrix of the restricted estimator, though it may be singular. In fact, $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)]$ is, in our case, a singular matrix because $\mathbf{R}' \left\{ \mathbf{R} \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)] \mathbf{R}' \right\}^{-1} \mathbf{R}$ is singular. Recall that, by construction, the j -th column of \mathbf{R}_j is zero.

Since \mathbf{A} is square, the unrestricted regression yields zero residuals. However, the constraints introduce non-zero residuals, enabling estimation of σ^2 (see Appendix A). The residual vector is:

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{E}_R) = \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}^*) - (\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}) \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R) \quad (9)$$

and the error variance is estimated as:

$$S^2 = \frac{\text{vec}(\mathbf{E}_R)' \text{vec}(\mathbf{E}_R)}{k(k-1)}. \quad (10)$$

2.2 Hypothesis Testing

This study aims to test hypotheses about the structure of \mathbf{B} , particularly $H_0: \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}_k$, which implies that $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_S = \boldsymbol{\Pi}_D = \mathbf{I}_k$, indicating no technological change. This hypothesis allows changes in production scale. Alternative hypotheses include $H_0: \mathbf{B} = \boldsymbol{\Pi}_S^{-1}$ (implying $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_D = \mathbf{I}_k$) and $H_0: \mathbf{B} = \boldsymbol{\Pi}_D$ (implying $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_S = \mathbf{I}_k$) though these require prior knowledge of technological change, which is often unavailable. To test $H_0: \text{vec}(\mathbf{B}) = \text{vec}(\mathbf{I}_k)$, we propose a Wald-type statistic.

$$W = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_q - \boldsymbol{\theta}_q)' \left[\text{var}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_q) \right]^{-1} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_q - \boldsymbol{\theta}_q) \sim \chi_{(q)}^2 \quad \text{under } H_0 \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R) = \text{vec}(\mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{A}^*)$, and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{I}_k)$ (the null hypothesis). The Wald statistic conditioned on \mathbf{A} , if $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)]^{-1}$ exists, is

$$W|\mathbf{A} = \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R - \mathbf{I}_k)' \left\{ \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)] \right\}^{-1} \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R - \mathbf{I}_k) \sim \chi_{(k^2)}^2 \quad (12)$$

But since $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)]$ is singular, we use the Moore-Penrose inverse and replace σ^2 with S^2 , yielding:

$$W^*|\mathbf{A} = \frac{\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R - \mathbf{I}_k)' \text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)]^+ \text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R - \mathbf{I}_k)/k^2}{\text{vec}(\mathbf{E}_R)' \text{vec}(\mathbf{E}_R)/(k^2 - k)} \quad (13)$$

where $\text{var}[\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)] = \mathbf{Q} - \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{R}'(\mathbf{R}\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{R}')^{-1}\mathbf{R}\mathbf{Q}$ and $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I}_k \otimes (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}$. Under H_0 , the statistic follows an $F_{(k^2; k^2-k)}$ distribution with degrees of freedom given by the non-zero terms of W^* (numerator) and the number of rows of $\mathbf{I}_k \otimes \mathbf{A}$, minus the columns, plus the constraints imposed on the model (denominator), that is, $k^2 - k^2 + k(k-1) = k(k-1)$.

3. Simulation

To determine the critical values of W^* , we simulated its distribution using fictitious SUTs of various dimensions, following these steps:

- Five pairs of SUTs with dimensions 5×3 , 30×10 , 60×20 , 100×30 , and 150×40 were constructed with random numbers. These dimensions reflect typical product-to-sector ratios in real SUTs, with the maximum size limited by computational capacity. The supply structure assigned each sector a primary product and several secondary products, potentially produced by related sectors. The use structure was dense, with no dominant inputs per sector. We ensured that each sector's gross production value exceeded its intermediate consumption and that total product supply was primarily absorbed by intermediate demand. These SUTs represented the true economy.
- Replicas of each SUT pair were generated by multiplying each element by a random factor $\sqrt{1 + 0.5 \times X}$, where $X \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$, yielding values between approximately 70% and 122% of the originals. For each replica, we computed \mathbf{A}^* , $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R$, and W^* . We used the Moore-Penrose inverse of $\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A}$ to compute $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R$ for numerical stability. The simulation was repeated 500 times per SUT pair. Figure 1 shows frequency histograms of W^* , and Table 1 lists the 80th, 85th, 90th, 95th, 97.5th, and 99th percentiles. These percentiles serve as critical values for W^* under the null hypothesis.
- For SUTs with dimensions not listed, critical values can be approximated using the empirical function:

$$\widehat{\ln \delta} = 0.12 - 0.68 \ln k + 1.45 (1 - \alpha) \ln k \quad (14)$$

where $\chi_{(k-\delta; 1-\alpha)}^2$ provides the critical value. For example, with $k = 35$ and $\alpha = 0.05$, $\hat{\delta} = 14$ (rounded), yielding $\chi_{(35-14, 0.95)}^2 = 32.67$. This formula extends Table 1 to larger SUTs, such as $k = 50$. The parameters were estimated by regression of empirically found δ on k and $(1 - \alpha) \ln k$.

Table 1: Percentiles 80 to 99 of the modified statistic W^* for five pairs of SUTs of dimension $n \times k$, obtained by simulation.

DIMENSIONS		PERCENTILES					
n	k	80	85	90	95	97.5	99
5	3	2.30	2.42	2.57	2.76	2.99	3.13
30	10	9.20	9.30	9.44	9.63	9.78	9.90
60	20	19.19	19.32	19.49	19.71	19.97	20.23
100	30	29.17	29.24	29.38	29.52	29.71	29.86
150	40	39.24	39.33	39.41	39.50	39.60	39.91

Figure 1: Frequency histograms of the statistic W^* simulated for SUTs of 10 to 40 sectors. Each plot summarizes 500 outcomes.

4. Conclusion

This paper proposes a statistical test to detect technological change, focusing on productivity increases from higher output without input substitution or reduced input use for the same output. Rejecting the null hypothesis indicates technological change in at least one economic sector. Formally, the test examines the hypotheses $H_0: \pi_j^D = \pi_j^S$ versus $H_1: \pi_j^D \neq \pi_j^S$, where π_j^S and π_j^D represent the j diagonal elements of the matrices $\mathbf{\Pi}_S$ and $\mathbf{\Pi}_D$, respectively. Here, π_j^S adjusts the production level of the j -th sector, and π_j^D adjusts input use. The test is unaffected by changes in production scale across sectors but does not detect technological changes involving labor-capital substitution with fixed inputs, such as learning-by-doing, which are rare at the aggregate level. Caution is advised for economies reliant on natural resources (e.g., agriculture or fishing), where productivity fluctuations may reflect external factors like climatic shocks rather than technological advancements. In such cases, we recommend decomposing the model as suggested by Frank (2024) and testing only the endogenous component's technical matrix.

The test statistic W^* follows a non-standard distribution rather than the expected F distribution, due to the use of a generalized inverse for $\text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R)$ and violations of Wald statistic assumptions, such as variance homogeneity. Critical values are provided for SUTs with 10 to 40 sectors (Table 1), with an empirical formula for interpolation or extrapolation to other dimensions. The test is independent of product classification but sensitive to sectoral classification, making comparisons across SUTs with different sectoral definitions unreliable. Similarly, W^* depends on the reference matrix \mathbf{A} , so comparisons must use the same \mathbf{A} (e.g., regressing multiple \mathbf{A}^* against a single \mathbf{A}).

The test extends to multiple periods using the generalized model:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_T \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A} & \dots & \mathbf{0}_{k \times k} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0}_{k \times k} & \dots & \mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A} \prod_{t=2}^T \mathbf{B}_t \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_1^F \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{d}_T^F \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_T$ and $\mathbf{d}_1^F, \dots, \mathbf{d}_T^F$ are the supply and final demand vectors for periods $1, \dots, T$. The hypothesis are:

$$\begin{cases} H_0: \mathbf{B}_1 = \dots = \mathbf{B}_T = \mathbf{I}_k, \\ H_1: \mathbf{B}_t \neq \mathbf{I}_k. \end{cases}$$

A more compact form is:

$$\text{vec}(\mathbf{X}) = [(\mathbf{I}_T \otimes \mathbf{I}_k) - (\mathbf{I}_T \otimes \mathbf{A})\mathbf{B}^*]^{-1} \text{vec}(\mathbf{D}_F) \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{B}^* is a block-diagonal matrix with \mathbf{I}_k as the first block and $\mathbf{B}_2, \dots, \mathbf{B}_T$ as subsequent blocks, and \mathbf{D}_F is the final demand matrix. By substituting \mathbf{A} with $\mathbf{I}_T \otimes \mathbf{A}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R$ with $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_R^*$ in equation (13), the test extends to multiple periods.

References

- Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Statistical Division (ed.) 1999. Handbook of Input-Output Table Compilation and Analysis. Studies in Methods. Series F No. 74. Handbook of National Accounting. United Nations. New York.
- Frank L., 2024. Multiplier Effects in the Input-Output Model with Two Exogenous Sectors. Zenodo, JSM Proceedings 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13820217>
- Greene W. H., & T. G. Seaks, 1991. The Restricted Least Squares Estimator: A Pedagogical Note. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 73(3): 563-567.
- Harville D., 1997. *Matrix Algebra From a Statistician's Perspective*. Springer-Verlag. New York.
- Kikawa C. R. & P. H. Kloppers, 2016. Multiple linear regression with constrained coefficients: Application of the Lagrange multiplier. *South African Statistical Journal* 50: 303-312.
- Lütkepohl H. (1996). *Handbook of Matrices*. John Wiley & Sons Ltd. Chichester. UK.
- Miller R. & P. Blair, 2009. *Input-Output Analysis. Foundations and Extensions*. 2nd Edition. Cambridge University Press.

A. Restricted Estimation

This involves optimizing the sum of squared errors function subject to a system of linear constraints on the model parameters. That is, the sum of squares $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}'\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is minimized subject to $\mathbf{R}\boldsymbol{\beta} = \mathbf{r}$. The objective function and the system of constraints are combined into a single function

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\lambda} | \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{y}) = (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})'(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}) + 2\boldsymbol{\lambda}'(\mathbf{R}\boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{r}) \quad (17)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is a vector of Lagrange multipliers of dimension $q \times k$, and \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{r} are known matrices of dimensions $q \times k$ and $q \times 1$. The Lagrange multipliers are multiplied by 2 for algebraic convenience. The first-order conditions of this optimization problem are

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{b}_R} = -2\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{y} + 2\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}\mathbf{b}_R + 2\mathbf{R}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}} = 2\mathbf{R}\mathbf{b}_R - 2\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The subscript R indicates that it is a restricted estimator, unlike the unrestricted estimator \mathbf{b}_{OLS} . Both equations can be combined into a single system of “normal” equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X} & \mathbf{R}' \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{0}_{q \times q} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_R \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{y} \\ \mathbf{0}_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

In the particular case of $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}_q$, the solution to the system of normal equations leads to

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{b}_R = \mathbf{b}_{OLS} - (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'[\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}\mathbf{b}_{OLS} \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = [\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}\mathbf{b}_{OLS} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

The variance of \mathbf{b}_R is easily obtained by rewriting the estimator expression more concisely as $\mathbf{b}_R = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})\mathbf{b}_{OLS}$,

$$var(\mathbf{b}_R) = var[(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})\mathbf{b}_{OLS}] = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})var(\mathbf{b}_{OLS})(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A}') \quad (21)$$

which, after some cancellations, reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} var(\mathbf{b}_R) &= var(\mathbf{b}_{OLS}) - \mathbf{A}var(\mathbf{b}_{OLS})\mathbf{A}' \\ &= \sigma^2(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1} - \sigma^2(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'[\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The reader can verify that the same result can be obtained by taking variances of the alternative expression $\mathbf{b}_R = \mathbf{b}_{OLS} - (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$ since

$$\begin{aligned} var(\mathbf{b}_R) &= var(\mathbf{b}_{OLS}) + var\left[(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}\right] + cov\left[\mathbf{b}_{OLS}, -\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}'\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\right] + \\ &\quad + cov\left[-(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}, \mathbf{b}'_{OLS}\right] \\ &= \sigma^2(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1} - \sigma^2(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'[\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

It is worth making a brief digression to define two operators that will be useful for estimating the error variance. Let

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{M} = \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}' \\ \mathbf{M}^* = \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'[\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}' \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Both \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{M}^* are symmetric and idempotent matrices, i.e., they are equal to their transposes, and $\mathbf{M}\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{M}$ and $\mathbf{M}^*\mathbf{M}^* = \mathbf{M}^*$. Moreover, it holds that $\mathbf{M}\mathbf{M}^* = \mathbf{M}^*$. Furthermore, the matrix $\mathbf{I}_n - (\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{M}^*)$ is also symmetric and idempotent, as can be seen

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^*)(\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^*) &= (\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M}) + (\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M})\mathbf{M}^* + \mathbf{M}^*(\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M}) + \mathbf{M}^*\mathbf{M}^* \\ &= \mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^* \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

This notation allows the predictor $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b}_R$ to be written concisely as

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{y}} &= \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b}_{OLS} - \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'[\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}\mathbf{b}_{OLS} \\ &= \mathbf{M}\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{M}^*\mathbf{y}\end{aligned}\tag{26}$$

so that the residual vector of the regression, $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{y} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}$, is

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{y} - (\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{M}^*)\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^*)\boldsymbol{\epsilon}\tag{27}$$

The steps leading to the replacement of \mathbf{y} with $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ can be found in regression texts. Then, the expectation of the squared residuals $E(\mathbf{e}'\mathbf{e}) = E[\text{tr}(\mathbf{e}\mathbf{e}')] is$

$$\begin{aligned}E(\mathbf{e}'\mathbf{e}) &= \text{tr}[(\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^*)E(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}\boldsymbol{\epsilon}')(\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^*)] \\ &= \sigma^2\text{tr}(\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{M}^*)\end{aligned}\tag{28}$$

As is known, $\text{tr}(\mathbf{I}_n) = n$, and using the trace rotation property, $\text{tr}(\mathbf{M}) = k$ and

$$\text{tr}(\mathbf{M}^*) = \text{tr}\left[\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}'[\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{R}']^{-1}\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\right] = \text{tr}(\mathbf{I}_q) = q$$

In conclusion,

$$E\left(\frac{\mathbf{e}'\mathbf{e}}{n - k + q}\right) = \sigma^2\tag{29}$$